

2nd European Congress of Health Sciences

May 4-5, 2024 - Bristow, VA / USA (ONLINE)
medjeur.com/congress

Oral Presentation-22

doi: 10.5281/zenodo.11107752

Protocols for Assessment and Treatment of Musculoskeletal Traumatic Injuries in the Shoulder Joint Complex: An Integrated Literature Review (ILR)

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RESUMO / ABSTRACT

Introduction: The shoulder joint complex is composed of several joints, with the main one being the glenohumeral, and a functional one called the scapulothoracic. Traumatic shoulder injuries are frequent, with an incidence of 33%, affecting mainly individuals under 40 years old. The most common causes are falls from own height (28.26%), motorcycle accidents (23.91%), falls from stairs, and direct trauma (8.7% each). Physiotherapeutic diagnosis is made through anamnesis and physical examinations, including inspection, palpation, range of motion assessment, muscle function tests, and special tests. Complementary exams such as magnetic resonance imaging and ultrasound can be used to assist in the diagnosis. **Objective:** To identify standardized protocols in the literature in the area of musculoskeletal rehabilitation and physiotherapy for painful conditions in the shoulder joint complex. **Methodology:** A literature review was conducted with a search in the databases of the Regional Portal of BVS, using the Health Sciences Descriptors (DeCS): "Physiotherapy," "Rehabilitation," "Shoulder," "Traumatic Injury," "Shoulder Injury," and "Car Accident," crossed between them. Articles that were not related to the studied theme were excluded. **Results:** Rehabilitation protocols aimed initially to relieve pain, improve range of motion, and strengthen the shoulder muscles. Combined therapies, such as electrotherapy and joint mobilization, were used, followed by proprioceptive neuromuscular facilitation (PNF) for range of motion gain. Muscle strengthening was performed with resisted training. The treatment also included the association of TENS with shoulder traction for joint decompression and pain relief, as well as specific exercises for range of motion and strength gain, such as Maitland Joint Mobilization Techniques, and for strengthening the scapular girdle, aiming at scapular stabilization and prevention of impacts on the humerus and its associated structures. **Conclusion:** Conservative treatment has shown effectiveness for traumatic shoulder injury, aiming at functional restoration, pain relief, range of motion gain, and improvement of muscle strength. Methods such as TENS, joint mobilizations, and PNF were effective for range of motion gain. Kinesiotherapy, with eccentric and concentric exercises, proved to be effective for muscle strength gain.

Keywords: Shoulder Joint Complex; PNF; Maitland; Glenohumeral

REFERENCES

1. BARBOSA, C. É. et al. Melhora na qualidade de vida e dor referida em trabalhadores com síndrome do impacto após a aplicação do método isotretching. *Acta Fisiátrica*, Campinas-São Paulo, v. 19, n. 3, p. 178-183.
2. CAIRES, S. L; JONER, C. Reabilitação fisioterapêutica no pós-operatório imediato e tardio de lesões do manguito rotador. 2018.
3. DEMENEZES, Mariana Cavalcante; DO SANTOS, Bárbara Sousa; GUERRA, Julyana Renata Fidelis. Importância da fisioterapia no tratamento da síndrome do impacto do ombro: relato de experiência. In: Congresso Brasileiro de Ciências da Saúde. 2016. p. 15-17.
4. SANTOS, A. A efetividade da mobilização passiva no tratamento de patologias do ombro. *Conscientiae Saúde Portugal*, v. 10, n. 2, 2011.